

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE RELOCATION POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN

Islam Kulturayev

Graduate student of KarshiDU

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ABSTRACT

Population migration to Uzbekistan was carried out in three directions: within the regions, outside the regions, and outside the republic. The article talks about the policy of relocating people to Uzbekistan, its causes and consequences.

The first stage of resettlement was carried out in 1926-1929, mainly in the form of resettlement of the population within the regions, during this period the scale of resettlement activities was small compared to those of the subsequent stages, only 8047 households moved to undeveloped areas inside the counties where they live.

The resettlement within the districts continued at the next stages. For example, in 1929-30, 2,400 households from Andijan district were moved to undeveloped areas in the district where they live. However, it was not possible to ensure the independence of cotton and eliminate the demographic problem only through internal relocations. As a result, the Soviet government took the resettlement work to a new level: since 1929, the resettlement of the population within the republic and between the republics began on a large scale.

The population will be relocated from Andijan, Fergana, Tashkent districts to undeveloped areas in Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, Surkhandarya districts. During the years 1929-1932, which is the second stage of the population resettlement campaign, about twenty thousand households were resettled.

Migrations outside the republic also have a special place in the policy of population relocation. In 1930, 510 farms (1530 people) were moved from Andijan district to the Caucasus. During the first five years, 7,312 farms were transferred from Fergana Valley districts to Tajikistan SSR. In this case, the resettlement of the farmers of the Fergana Valley was not only related to easing the demographic tension, but also related to their experience in the field of cotton cultivation and its dissemination.

As the resettlement was aimed at ensuring the independence of cotton, not only farmers were mobilized, but the entire population of high-density areas was mobilized. However, the main majority were peasants. In the early years, individual households were resettled, but later it was recognized that the natural desire of the peasants to support their families interferes with the general work, and they moved to family-based resettlement¹. In

¹ Shamsiddinov R. Qishloq fojeasi: jamoalashtirish, quloqlashtirish, surgun. T.Sharq. 2003. 10-11 b.

addition, since the population resettlement policy is aimed at solving the problem of land scarcity, the landless or land-poor strata were relocated. In rare cases, rich kulak farms were also forcibly relocated. Sometimes they served as shelters for those who were on the "black list" of the government. In densely populated central regions, persecuted by the government, some "class alien elements" who instinctively tried to save their lives saw no other way than to apply to resettlement funds.

The policy of resettlement attracted not only Uzbeks, but also representatives of other nationalities. In 1929-1934, 6,312 representatives of other nationalities were resettled, the nomadic part of Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, and Turkmens were also resettled to undeveloped territories under the pretext of settlement. In the process of resettlement of the population, the issue of involving the people in the resettlement policy was singled out as a separate issue. Until that time, the Jews, whose source of livelihood was small crafts or trade, were forced to engage in agriculture. In the second phase of the resettlement campaign, 1,061 Jewish households were relocated. In addition, Russians, Poles, Germans and other peoples, who are not familiar with the science of cotton cultivation, were involved in the policy of population relocation. This was the origin of the government's violence in national politics.

In Uzbekistan in the 30s of the last century, under the guise of total collectivization of agriculture, when the mass repressions in the villages escalated, peasant families exiled as "kulaks" were placed in special settlements under the control of the General Directorate of Camps (GULAG) of the OGPU. In 1930-1934, the deportees were called "special exiles" (spets-vreselensi) in official documents.

In 1934, when the OGPU was reorganized as the NKVD (People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs), changes took place in the GULAG management structure. From this period, the term "labor refugees" (trudposepense) began to be used instead of the term "special forced laborers". Settlements that are located in Kulakpar will be called "labor settlement" and not "special settlement".

In 1936-1937, labor settlements were almost organized and organized into a certain system. During this period, there were 15 villages in Uzbekistan where kulak households were settled. district) was in the tribe. In the following years, the number of labor settlements decreased, their names and numbers also changed

In 1937, there were 3,538 kulak families (13,924 people) in existing labor settlements in Uzbekistan. 7,054 of the displaced people were able to work, and they worked in 134 labor brigades. The population of the settlement changed depending on the number of births and deaths. At the same time, the cases of refugees fleeing from labor settlements also affected this indicator.

It is known that in 1937-1938, the authoritarian regime intensified mass repressions on all fronts. This situation left an ominous mark on those exiled to special settlements on July 2, 1937. a directive decision is taken. In this directive, it was noted that former Kulaks and criminals who fled from exile have settled in all cities and villages of the Union, and they are engaged in anti-Soviet subversive activities in industrial enterprises, collective farms and state farms, transport and other production sectors. In the directive decision, the composition of the "triads" sentencing such "elements", as well as the number of those to be sentenced to

death and exiled, were assigned to be submitted to the Central Committee of the VKP(b) within five days².

At the meeting of the Political Bureau of the Central Committee of the VKP(b) on July 11, 1937, the composition of the "troika" for the Uzbek-Kistan SSR was Zagvozdin (People's Commissar of Internal Affairs of the UzSSR), Ikramov (Secretary of the Central Committee of the UzKP(b)), Boltaboyev (Chairman of the UzSSR Central Committee) was formed on July 30, 1937, on the basis of the decision of the Political Bureau of the Central Committee of the VKP(b) on July 2, No. 00447 of the NKVD of the UzSSR "Operation to suppress former kulaks, criminals and other anti-Soviet elements" the operative command "about" is issued.

In order to ruthlessly crush these "anti-Soviet elements", the NKVD authorities are assigned the task of starting a repressive operation starting from August 5, 1937 and completing it within four months. In this way, mass repression will increase in Uzbekistan. From August 10, 1937 to January 1, 1938, 5924 people from "kulags", 1679 people from "criminals", 3097 people from other "anti-Soviet elements", a total of 10700 people were imprisoned in Uzbekistan. Among them, 3613 people were sentenced to death under the 1st category, and 7087 people were sentenced to a labor-reform camp for 8-10 years under the 2nd category.

A certain part of those who were repressed were former "kulaks" - labor refugees, who are suffering exile in labor settlements. The former "kulaks" who were punished during the years of collective collectivization will again be subjected to repression during the period of "great terror". Since 1934, the NKVD bodies have consistently established agency work in labor settlements. In most cases, the information of this agency served as a sufficient basis for repressing labor migrants.

The "troika" of the NKVD of the USSR sentenced an average of 310-315 people at each meeting. Most of the time, the "troika" made hasty judgments based on the indictments received from the NKVD sectors in the places. At this point, it is enough to cite the example of gross violation of the procedural law during the investigation in the Andijan sector alone. Employees of the NKVD Andijan sector - the former head of the sector A.A. Stasin, his deputy A.V. Kulinichev, the beginning of the 4th department Makarevichs in 1938 for falsifying criminal cases, confirming investigative documents and preparing illegal drafts of sentences against many prisoners He was sentenced to the highest punishment by the Military Tribunal of the Asian Military District.

The permanent detention of labor migrants in labor settlements naturally limited their rights and freedoms. That is why it is common for them to run away from labor settlements. After all, it was easier to escape from the settlement than to escape from prison or a camp.

It can be said that no thorough search was conducted for the runaway workers. This situation did not affect the year by year decrease of the working population in labor settlements. The saddest thing is that those who fled from the labor settlements became one of the main objects of repression during the "great terror". The collection of archival documents also contains information about the persecution of hundreds of former kulaks who escaped from the "exile of kulaks" and entered collective farms in Ukraine, the North Caucasus, northern Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan³.

² Abdullayev M. Sho'ro davridagi "quloq" pasyolkalari //Tafakkur ,T, 2011. 91-92 bet

³ Shamsiddinov.R. O'zbekistonda sovetlarning quloqlashtirish siyosati va uning fojeali oqibatlarini. T. Sharq, 2001. 32b.

However, most of the displaced laborers lived in a poor condition and were up to their ears in debt. For this reason, authorities and NKVD offices have been applying to higher authorities with proposals to cancel the debts of labor migrants and extend the loan repayment period. In some cases, these proposals have been positively resolved. For example, by the decision of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR dated April 21, 1937 No. SO-1219, labor migrants were exempted from debt on loans⁴.

In 1939, the scale of repression decreased sharply. This year, the number of people repressed due to "deportation of ears" will decrease 9 times compared to previous years. As of January 1, 1939, 987,918 labor migrants were registered in the Union, and 2,644 people (0.27%) were convicted this year. During this period, there were 14,312 labor migrants in Uzbekistan, and 17 people (0.11 percent) were sentenced this year.

In short, during the years of mass repressions, the "kulaks" who were exiled to special settlements will again be subjected to repressions. A certain part of the repressive measures set by the Soviet government for the republic will be fulfilled at the expense of labor migration. Penal institutions did not hesitate to fulfill the task of the "higher". The law authorities of the autocratic regime have recognized the widespread use of illegal means such as torture and psychological influence on the detainees in order to "make them confess their guilt".

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INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY

⁴ Abdullayev M. Sho'ro davridagi "quloq" pasyolkalari T.: Tafakkur jurnali 2011. 91-92 6er